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Proof-of-concept of a solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft digital twin targeting Mars and its moons.

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FENG 498

Final Report

**Proof-of-concept of a solar-sail propelled CubeSat class
spacecraft digital twin targeting Mars and its moons**

Furkan Arda Tigrik¹, Berkay Burak Toker¹

today

Abstract

The idea of a "Digital-Twin" has received a lot of attention in the field of space travel. A [Digital-Twin](#), which enables real-time monitoring, analysis, and predictive modeling, is a virtual replica or simulation of a real system, such a spacecraft. This article aims to describe a new concept, the [Digital-Twin](#), and show how it can be used for space missions. Using Free Open Source Softwares, the main purpose is to simulate the spacecraft going to mars with solar sailler and create a digital copy of the mission by getting realistic results. Diagrams of open source programs used to solve problems that may be encountered in this process are included.

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List of Symbols and Acronyms

6-DOF Six degree of freedom. three translational and three rotational motion. [2](#), [27–29](#)

AU Astronomical unit [9](#), [37](#)

DCM Direction cosine matrix. A matrix that converts one vector to another reference frame. [2](#), [13](#), [15](#), [16](#), [28](#), [41–45](#)

Digital-Twin It can be simply described as a virtual model of the real object and its environment. [1](#), [5](#), [27](#), [49](#), [50](#)

DP Double polarization [6](#)

FOSS It represents Free Open Source Softwares that includes some softwares like Xcos, Scilab and OpenModelica which are also used in this paper. [27](#)

GEO Geosynchronous earth orbit. [12](#)

NED A traditional axes system. North, East, Down [28](#)

PLM Product lifecycle management. [5](#)

RMSE Root mean square error. [6](#)

Scilab An open source software developed to simulate or solve systems or equations numerically. FOSS equivalent of MATLAB. [2](#), [5–8](#), [19](#), [27](#)

SOC State of charge [6–8](#)

Xcos Block based dynamic system modeling and numerical equation solving program [2](#), [5–8](#), [19](#), [27–29](#), [37](#), [39](#), [41](#), [43](#), [47](#), [48](#)

1 Introduction

Mars missions are very important for humanity, these missions contribute to the development of technology in different fields and the exploration of the galaxy we are in. We can list such topics as follows.

Scientific Discovery: Mars missions help us better comprehend the Red Planet's geology, its past, and any potential signs of life there now or in the past. Scientists may examine the soil, rocks, and atmospheric conditions on Mars with rovers, landers, and orbiters, which helps them understand the planet's previous temperature, water cycles, and potential for habitability. Our understanding of planetary formation and evolution is improved by this information, which also sheds light on Earth's own history.

Search for Life: Finding evidence of past or current life is one of the main goals of Mars missions. Scientists can assess whether life ever existed on Mars by examining its geology and climate, which were originally thought to have circumstances favorable for supporting life. Such findings would fundamentally alter how we perceive the origins of life and shed light on the likelihood of life existing elsewhere in the universe.

Technological Innovation: Mars missions act as a catalyst for new developments. Engineering, robotics, and space systems are pushed to their limits by the difficulties of reaching and exploring Mars. Propulsion, life support, navigation, and communication system advancements can have a wide range of uses, advancing technologies across many industries and helping mankind as a whole.

Mars missions act as stepping stones for upcoming crewed trips to Mars in the context of human space exploration. Scientists can obtain important information on radiation exposure, the impact of long-duration space travel on the human body, and the difficulties of surviving and operating in harsh settings by launching robotic missions. These discoveries assist in the creation of fundamental technologies and procedures needed for future Martian exploration and settlement by humans.

Mars missions also play a significant part in planetary protection. To prevent the contamination of Mars with Earth's germs and vice versa, strict precautions are implemented. This makes it possible to positively link any putative life forms to Mars rather than to contamination from Earth if they are ever found. These safety measures safeguard the prospect of discovering native Martian life as well as the scientific integrity of next expeditions.

Public Engagement and Inspiration: Mars missions capture the public's imagination and serve as a source of motivation for upcoming generations of scientists, engineers, and explorers. These missions' audacity and complexity inspire awe and a sense of potential in young people, motivating

them to seek professions in STEM disciplines. Innovation is stimulated and a worldwide interest in science and space exploration is fostered by a shared desire to explore and push boundaries.

Resources and sustainability: Mars missions provide information about possible resources on the planet, including water ice, minerals, and regolith. For sustainable exploration and perhaps long-term human settlements, it is essential to comprehend the use and accessibility of these resources. Local resource extraction increases prospects for interplanetary trade and self-sufficiency while reducing reliance on Earth.

For such reasons, this research is about a Mars mission. The spacecraft considered to complete this task is a CubeSat powered by solar sails, the specific issue being to replicate this task exactly using free open source applications. These apps were mostly [Xcos](#), a plugin from [Scilab](#). With its block structure, it has enabled the environment and spacecraft to be simulated with real values. The diagram created by including these environmental factors is called [Digital-Twin](#). Since the idea of a [Digital-Twin](#) has been around for a while, it is challenging to pinpoint a specific person or organization as its originator. However, Dr. Michael Grieves, a professor at the Florida Institute of Technology, was the one who initially came up with and popularized the phrase "[Digital-Twin](#)" in the early 2000s. In the course of his investigation on the use of [PLM](#) in the aerospace sector, he suggested the idea. As time passed, it started to be used by different companies in different fields. At the same time, studies on this subject have increased. This concept, which has started to be talked about more recently, can calculate not only an object, but also all kinds of situations that can be experienced in real life, unlike simulations. For example, considering the condition of a racing car on the track, the optimum lap time of this vehicle can be calculated under ideal conditions with simulations. However, with the [Digital-Twin](#) of this vehicle, it is possible to obtain results that are much closer to reality by including many variables such as the asphalt condition of the track, weather conditions, instantly changing tire conditions, the efficiency of the vehicle's engine and the loss of power that the engine can transfer to the wheels. By applying such situations to CubeSat, it is aimed to create a realistic twin of the mission by evaluating and bringing together factors such as the instantaneous positions of the planets, the instantaneous speed of the CubeSat, the instantaneous thrust and moment produced by the solar sails.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Arianto S et al, Development of single cell lithium ion battery model using [Scilab/Xcos](#), AIP Conference Proceedings 1711, 060007 (2016) [1]

The electrochemical model and the electrical circuit model are the two fundamental models that make up the battery model. The reduced electrochemical model and the electrical circuit model are combined to create the dynamic battery model. Analytical models and mathematical models are categories for other models. The nonlinear partial differential equations generated by the electrochemical model have a substantial number of unknown parameters, necessitating a significant amount of computing power and time for computer simulation. As a result, it is

inappropriate for BMS applications that need to monitor and regulate data in real-time.

Three categories of electrical circuit models exist: the Rint, Thevenin, and DP models. Due to its simplicity, quick computation times, and precise modeling of lithium battery dynamics, the DP model is employed in this study. Due to its minimal mistakes and low RMSE, it is the best model when compared. The three electrical circuit models, V OC, R i, R S, and C L, describe the battery's internal resistance, open circuit voltage, and rapid and slow dynamic responses.

Figure 1: Electrical circuit models: (a) Rint Model, (b) Thevenin model, and (c) DP model

The DP model redraws to calculate SOC and shows the dependent of circuit parameters on SOC. It includes a DC voltage source (V OC) dependent on SOC, a series resistance (Ri) representing internal dc resistance, and parallel RC networks (R S, C S, R L, C L). V batt and I batt, respectively, stand for the battery voltage and current. With a constant current of 9.3 Ampere and an initial SOC of 100% , the proposed battery model block is demonstrated while being discharged.

Figure 2: The proposed model of lithium battery in Scilab/Xcos

Five computational blocks make up the suggested model in [Scilab/Xcos](#) for calculating battery voltage and **SOC** when running the battery. Among these blocks are the Voltage of RC Networks Calculation block, the **SOC** Calculation block, the RC Calculation block, the V OC Calculation block, and the V i Calculation block. The battery voltage and the current state of charge are output by the model, which also takes load/charger current and the beginning state of charge as inputs. The parameters are shown as polynomial **SOC** functions, which are obtained from experimental curve fitting data.

Figure 3: **SOC** Calculation and V_i Calculation

The **SOC** calculation involves calculating the battery's initial value, I_{batt} , E_{ff} , C_{cap} , and **SOC** in percentage unit. The efficiency is 0.99, and the usable capacity is 9.3 Ah. The calculation block is shown in this figure.

$$SOC(t) = SOC_0 - \frac{E_{ff}}{C_{cap}} \int_{t_0}^t \frac{I_{batt} \times 100}{3600} dt \quad (1)$$

The values of V_{OC} , R_i , R_S , C_S , R_L , and C_L are calculated using their respective polynomial functions with **SOC** as independent variables because all parameter data are curve fitted using polynomials. The polynomial function used to determine V_{OC} is shown in second equation. Curve fitting of the data was used to determine the coefficients of that function.

$$V_{(oc)} = 2908.89 + 44.3 * SOC - 1.98316 * SOC^2 - 0.0416 * SOC^3 - 4.08 * 10^{-4} * SOC^4 + 1.51 * 10^{-5} * SOC^5 \quad (2)$$

I_{batt} and R_i are simply multiplied to get V_i , and R_i is determined using a polynomial function. The voltage drop V_i is represented by the internal dc resistance R_i . Third equation displays the

formula for computing V_i , and Figure illustrates how it is implemented in [Scilab/Xcos](#).

$$V_i = I_{batt} R_i \quad (3)$$

To determine the voltages of two RC parallel networks, RC values are required. The values of RC parallel networks are assessed using polynomial functions, and they solely depend on [SOC](#). The implementation of computing RC values in [Scilab/Xcos](#) is shown in Figure. Using the values of the determined RC and Equations, computing blocks in Figure are utilized to calculate the voltage of V_S and V_L . Equation is then used to determine the battery voltage, which is then implemented in [Scilab/Xcos](#) in Figure.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_S &= -\frac{V_S}{R_S C_S} + \frac{I_{batt}}{C_S} \\ \dot{V}_L &= -\frac{V_L}{R_L C_L} + \frac{I_{batt}}{C_L} \\ V_{batt} &= V_{OC} - I_{batt} R_i - V_S - V_L \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Figure 4: RC Calculation and V_s , V_L Calculation

2.2 Wertz James Richard David F Everett and Jeffery John Puschell.. Space Mission Engineering : The New Smad. Hawthorne CA: Microcosm Press. [2]

Solar sailing makes use of the energy and momentum from light, but it does not use solar cells to turn it into electrical energy or solar wind to transfer momentum. Light pressure is more effective than solar sailing because of the low density of ionized particles. However, because of their constant momentum change and lightweight propellant, solar sails are most useful for trips around

Mars' orbit. To change the orbital altitude in relation to celestial bodies like the Sun, planets, moon, asteroids, or comets, solar sails can produce a small amount of propulsion. Prograde propulsion elevates the orbit while retrograde thrust lowers it by angling the sail to direct the push component parallel to the orbit velocity vector. Figure 18-14 shows the geometric relationship between solar sail orientation and incoming light.

The thrust on a flat solar sail is perpendicular to the surface of the sail with magnitude given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F &= (2RSA/C) \sin^2 \theta \\
 &= 9.113 \times 10^{-6} \left(RA/D^2 \right) \sin^2 \theta
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5}$$

where, in the second form, F is in Newtons, R is the fraction of incident light reflected by the sail (maximum of 1), D is the distance from the Sun to the solar sail in AU, S is the solar flux in W/m^2 , A is the sail area in m^2 , c is the speed of light, and θ is the sail tilt angle the angle between the Sun-Earth line and the sail.

Due to the fact that solar sail performance involves more than just the reflectance factor, it does not account for all the variables that translate into the force caused by light pressure. On realistic "grey" solar sails with finite transmittance and absorptance and imperfect reflectance, which was further divided into specular, diffuse, and back reflectance, Forward examined the impacts of different optical qualities.

For solar sails to minimize mass for multiple hundred kilogram payloads, a thin material is needed, like aluminum film. A polymer substrate that degrades in the presence of ultraviolet light, leaving just the aluminum film, is one possibility for coating the aluminum film on. Another possibility is to pierce solar sails with holes eight times smaller in diameter than the wavelength of light. Carbon fibers with an aluminum coating are another option. When designing a solar sail, there are a number of things to take into account, beginning with the choice of sail material and aspects like reflectivity, fragility, and lifetime. In comparison to gold (reflectivity 20%-100%, 19.32 g/cm^3), silver (reflectivity 0%-100%, 10.49 g/cm^3), and copper (8.96 g/cm^3), aluminum has a high reflectivity (86%-97% for wavelengths from about 0.2 to 1.5 μm) and a low density (2.70 g/cm^3). All viable materials are delicate at the required thicknesses, although rip stops can be added to reduce ripping, which is most likely to happen during use.

Figure 5: General Depiction of How Solar Sails Maneuver

Figure 6: Defining Solar Sail Equation Geometrical Relationships

The three primary types of solar sails are helio gyro, square, and circular. Booms are needed for the square sail arrangement to support the sail material; available options include inflatable, composite, and open truss structures. Although the 4-boom structure is physically effective, it has important implications for deployment reliability and bulk. Tip vanes and a mobile center of mass can be employed together to control attitude. While the helio gyro configuration requires significant edge tendons along the blades to sustain centrifugal forces, the circular configuration necessitates displacement of the center of mass concerning pressure. Although the circular shape is easier, a

square sail has greater mass efficiency.

<p>ADVANTAGES</p> <p>Not propellant limited, as is the case for chemical, electric, and nuclear</p> <p>Can achieve orbits not achievable by any other means or achievable only to a limited extent (e.g., cylindrical orbits, retrograde solar orbits)</p> <p>Permits efficient use of geosynchronous altitude by allowing stacking of multiple satellites at the same longitude</p> <p>Can perform dual roles [applies to, for example, transfers associated with going to and from geosynchronous Earth orbit (GEO) or transfers to and from another planet]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Boost payload to desired orbit and maintain orbit• Boost payload to desired orbit, drop it off, and return for another payload <p>Minimal to no orbit debris</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Can return payloads for repair• Can place payload on a trajectory to burn up in the atmosphere or boost it into a safe orbit <p>Very large, thus very visible</p> <p>For comparable missions, fewer spacecraft required (e.g., GEO communications satellite, see Fig. 18-16—levitated orbit allows cross pole communications with 2 spacecraft instead of 3 needed to send signals "around" the geosynchronous belt)</p>
<p>DISADVANTAGES</p> <p>Very little operational experience when compared to chemical or electric propulsion</p> <p>Complex deployment, independent of configuration</p> <p>Requires continuous control to maintain desired orientation</p> <p>Main benefit for inner planet missions (similar to solar electric)</p> <p>Vulnerable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• To attack• From orbital debris• From micrometeorites <p>Long time required to spiral out to desired orbit when compared to other propulsion technologies, such as chemical and nuclear (for interplanetary missions, an option is to use chemical propulsion for Earth escape)</p> <p>Very large, thus very visible</p> <p>Higher performance versions require space fabrication</p>

Figure 7: Table of Advantages and Disadvantages

Advantages

- . Not restricted by propellant, as with chemical, electric, and nuclear
- . Can reach orbits that are either impossible to reach by other methods or only partially possible (such as cylinder orbits and retrograde solar orbits).
- . Allows for the efficient slacking of several satellites at the same longitude, which maximizes the usage of geosynchronous height.
- . Can play two roles (this includes, for instance, transfers to and from GEO or to and from another planet).
- . Boost the payload to the required orbit and keep it there. Boost the payload to the desired orbit, drop it off, and then come back for another payload.
- . Low to no orbital debris; return of payloads for maintenanceCan place payload on a trajectory to burn up in the atmosphere or boost it into a safe orbit Very large, thus very visible

Disadvantages

- . Compared to chemical or electric propulsion, very limited operational experience deployment that is complex and configuration-independent continual control is needed to keep the proper orientation
- . The primary advantage for missions to inner planets (similar to solar energy)
- . Vulnerable to attack, orbital debris, micrometeorites, and attack
- . Compared to other propulsion systems like chemical and nuclear, spiraling out to the desired orbit takes a long time (chemical propulsion for Earth escape is an option for interplanetary missions).
- . Very massive and noticeable
- . Versions with higher performance require space manufacture

2.3 Performance, Stability, Dynamics, and Control of Airplanes, Second Edition, Bandu N. Pamadi, 2004, AIAA, ISBN 1-56347-583-9 [3]

Chapter 4 of the book deals with the determination of equations of motion and stability derivatives. Of course, the basic information necessary to derive and use equations of motion has already started at the beginning of the chapter with the study of axis systems and the transformations between these systems. The reason why the axis sets are so diverse can be said that various reference axis sets are more suitable for the analytical or numerical solution of the mathematical model of any

system. The person who will make the calculations can choose the most suitable axes and make the operations simpler and easier. It can also make conversions between these axis systems using [DCM](#).

The most well-known of these axes are shown below.

Inertial Axis System:

This set of axes can simply be defined as a stationary system that does not rotate around itself and does not perform translational motion. Since the acceleration of an object calculated according to Newton's 2nd law ($F = m * a$) is calculated according to a stationary axis system, it is essential to use such a stationary axes set. Generally, for calculations on the earth, a system of motionless axis with origin at the center of the earth is used, in which the rotation of the earth is neglected in most cases.

Axes System Fixed to Earth:

This axis set is also an axis system in which the rotation of the earth is not neglected and the rotation speed of the axis system is the same as that of the Earth.

Navigational Axis System:

The center of this set of axes is usually located on any object on the Earth's surface, while the classical x and z axes point to the north and center of the Earth, while the y-axis is determined by the right-hand rule.

Body Axes System:

This axis set can be generally defined as an axis system that moves with the body and whose center is usually the body's center of mass. Traditionally, the x-axis is the direction the vehicle is going, for the airplane, the y-axis is pointing to the right of the pilot, and in accordance with the right-hand rule, the z-axis is pointing to the bottom of the vehicle. Of course, these systems that rotate and shift with the body are not one. Two of the most familiar body axes are stability and wind axis systems.

Stability Axis System:

The x-direction of this axis system is in the opposite direction to the velocity vector obtained by projecting the relative velocity vector relative to the aircraft on the plane of symmetry of the aircraft. The angle between the x-direction of this axis set and the x-direction of the hull axis set is commonly referred to as the angle of attack. The y-direction is in line with the y-axis of the body pivot assembly. The z-direction is downwards in accordance with the right hand rule and the body axis makes an angle of attack with the z-direction.

Wind Axis System:

In this axis system, the x direction is directly opposite to the velocity vector, and the y and z directions are the result of rotation from the body axis according to the angle of attack and slip angle of the velocity vector with the body axis.

After introducing the familiar axis systems, it is shown how to transform between these axes with the help of the rotation angles given according to the axes. Three different methods are mentioned in the book. These are;

- . Euler angles
- . Direction cosine matrix
- . quaternions

Euler angles indicate the orientation of any reference system with respect to the Earth. These are symbolized as ϕ , θ and ψ , respectively. As can be seen from the figure below, the angle ϕ represents rotations on the x-axis, the angle θ represents the rotations on the y-axis, and the angle ψ represents the rotations on the z-axis.

Fig. 4.3 Euler angles.

Figure 8: Euler angles and axes transformation

Of course, these angles must have certain limits, otherwise axis conflicts, also called gimbal locks, may occur and dualities may occur. Therefore:

Also, attention should be paid to the rotation sequence when rotating the axes. For example,

$$-\pi \leq \psi \leq \pi$$

$$-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$$

$$-\pi \leq \phi \leq \pi$$

the situation in the result of an axis system rotated with ZYX order is not necessarily the same as the situation in the result of an axis system rotated with angular magnitudes but with YXZ order.

In this section of the book, the axis system resulting from an axes rotated in ZYX order and its expression in matrix terms (ie. **DCM**) are shown. First, if the system is rotated by the angle ψ from the Z axis:

$$x'_1 = x_1 \cos \psi + y_1 \sin \psi$$

$$y'_1 = -x_1 \sin \psi + y_1 \cos \psi$$

$$z'_1 = z_1$$

or in matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x'_1 \\ y'_1 \\ z'_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ -\sin \psi & \cos \psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \\ z_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ -\sin \psi & \cos \psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Likewise, if it is rotated from the Y-axis with an angle of ψ :

$$x''_1 = x'_1 \cos \theta - z'_1 \sin \theta$$

$$y''_1 = y'_1$$

$$z''_1 = x'_1 \sin \theta + z'_1 \cos \theta$$

or in matrix form:

If rotated from the x-axis by an angle of ψ :

or in matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1'' \\ y_1'' \\ z_1'' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1' \\ y_1' \\ z_1' \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x_1''' = x_1''$$

$$y_1''' = y_1'' \cos \phi + z_1'' \sin \phi$$

$$z_1''' = -y_1'' \sin \phi + z_1'' \cos \phi$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1''' \\ y_1''' \\ z_1''' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \phi & \sin \phi \\ 0 & -\sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1'' \\ y_1'' \\ z_1'' \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \phi & \sin \phi \\ 0 & -\sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{bmatrix}$$

ABC is obtained. And the following equality can be obtained: Then, if these three matrices are

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1''' \\ y_1''' \\ z_1''' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} = A \begin{bmatrix} x_1'' \\ y_1'' \\ z_1'' \end{bmatrix} = ABC \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \\ z_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

multiplied with each other in the form of matrix multiplication with ABC order, [DCM](#), which will express this rotation movement, is found as:

$$T_1^2 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta \cos \psi & \cos \theta \sin \psi & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta \sin \phi \cos \psi - \sin \psi \cos \phi & \sin \psi \sin \theta \sin \phi + \cos \psi \cos \phi & \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ \sin \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi + \sin \psi \sin \phi & \sin \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi - \cos \psi \sin \phi & \cos \phi \cos \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

Since all of the ABC matrices forming this matrix, which provides the transition from the 1st state to the 2nd state, or in other words, from the ground to the body, are orthogonal matrices, this is equal to the inverse transpose of the last matrix. Therefore: In this way, the matrix expressing the transition from the body to the ground can be written as seen above.

$$T_2^1 = (T_1^2)^{-1} = (T_1^2)' \quad (4.24)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta \cos \psi & \sin \theta \sin \phi \cos \psi - \sin \psi \cos \phi & \sin \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi + \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \cos \theta \sin \psi & \sin \psi \sin \theta \sin \phi + \cos \psi \cos \phi & \sin \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi - \cos \psi \sin \phi \\ -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta & \cos \phi \cos \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

2.4 Stevens, Brian L. and Lewis, Frank L. 1992, Aircraft control and simulation, Brian L. Stevens, Frank L. Lewis Wiley New York [4]

In the "Angular Motion" section, which begins in the "Equations of Motion" section of the book, the moments (ie torques) created by the forces created by either the thrust vector control or control surfaces in an aircraft and therefore not occurring at the vehicle's center of mass are mentioned.

The explanation of Newton's 2nd law for rotational motion is illustrated by the following symbolization:

$$\mathbf{T}_B = \frac{d\mathbf{H}_B}{dt_I} \quad (6)$$

Here, $\mathbf{T}_B$ is the moment or torque in the body-axis, and $\frac{d\mathbf{H}_B}{dt_I}$ is the rate of change of angular momentum in the body-axis, with respect to the ground axis and time. In order to determine the angular momentum vector, the linear momentum of any unit mass (δm) is found first.

$$\delta(\text{momentum}) = (\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{r}) \delta m.$$

Then, the "angular momentum" of this particle is calculated as the moment of linear momentum and shown as follows.

$$\delta\mathbf{H}_B = [\mathbf{r} \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{r})] \delta m.$$

If the components of the vectors $\boldsymbol{\omega}_B$ and $\mathbf{r}$ are given conventional nomenclature as follows: The

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_B = P\mathbf{i} + Q\mathbf{j} + R\mathbf{k}$$

$$\mathbf{r} = x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k},$$

angular momentum of this particle can be unfolded as follows: Afterwards, this angular momentum

$$\delta\mathbf{H}_B = \begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \\ R \end{bmatrix} (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) \delta m - \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} (Px + Qy + Rz) \delta m.$$

$$\mathbf{H}_B = \begin{bmatrix} P \int (y^2 + z^2) dm - Q \int xy dm - R \int xz dm \\ Q \int (x^2 + z^2) dm - R \int yz dm - P \int yx dm \\ R \int (x^2 + y^2) dm - P \int zx dm - Q \int zy dm \end{bmatrix}$$

equation obtained only for a unit particle with mass δm can be integrated for all unit particles on the object, and the total angular momentum of the object can be found in vector form as follows. It can be noticed that some expressions in the vector correspond to expressions such as cross-product moment of inertia of the object in certain axes. As it can be noticed when these expressions are

$$\text{moment of inertia about } x\text{-axis} = J_{xx} = \int (y^2 + z^2) dm$$

$$\text{cross-product of inertia } J_{xy} \equiv J_{yx} = \int xy dm.$$

written instead, the angular momentum vector can be written as the product of the moment of inertia matrix and the angular velocity vector.

$$\mathbf{H}_B = \begin{bmatrix} J_{xx} & -J_{xy} & -J_{xz} \\ -J_{xy} & J_{yy} & -J_{yz} \\ -J_{xz} & -J_{yz} & J_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \\ R \end{bmatrix} \equiv J \boldsymbol{\omega}_B$$

After expressing the angular momentum vector as the product of the inertia matrix and the angular velocity vector, the equation in equation 6 can be applied. The derivative of the angular momentum vector was found by the Coriolis theorem, which was also shown in this book, and since Newton's second law was written for the invariant mass, the moment of inertia matrix was assumed to be constant. Of course, in real-life applications, this assumption is sometimes wrong, more or less, due to situations such as an aircraft or another vehicle leaving a load or a decrease in fuel. However, such an acceptance has been made in terms of simplicity of expression and ease of operation.

With these assumptions, Newton's second law for rotation (equation 6) began to be differentiated.

$$\dot{\mathbf{H}}_B + \boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{H}_B = \mathbf{T}_B$$

And as a result, the angular acceleration vector of the body relative to the ground can be written as the following equation:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_B = -J^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times (J\boldsymbol{\omega}_B)) + J^{-1}T_B \quad (7)$$

equation 7 is a general equation expressing angular motion. It expresses a relationship between angular acceleration and torque (ie moment), angular velocity and moment of inertia relative to the ground on the body axis.

3 Methodology

3.1 Fabrizio Pinto. (8 May 2023). Scilab/Xcos simulations of Lightsail 2 (2D) (Jupyter Notebook, v 1.0). Retrieved from: Open Science Framework: <https://osf.io/tehp2/>. Project: Algorithms, codes, and data acquisition procedures developed by Fabrizio Pinto either as original tools or from the referenced literature. Component: Elements of solar sailing.

In our previous academic article, we simulated the harmonic oscillator situation we designed with Xcos and openmodelica, this time by installing Scilab on jupyternotebook.

3.1.1 Harmonic Oscillator

As a first step we implement equation of motion for harmonic oscillator.

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} + \frac{\gamma}{m}\dot{x} + \omega_0^2 x &= 0, \\ x(t=0) &= 1, \dot{x}(0) = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

After that in order to show damped harmonic oscillator γ have to be greater than 0. To show that its set as: $\gamma/m = 0.1$

With using that formula below discontinuous harmonic oscillator can be obtain.

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} &= \begin{cases} -4x, & \text{if } t \leq 6 \text{ s} \\ -2x, & \text{if } 12 \text{ s} \geq t > 6 \text{ s} \\ -8x, & \text{if } 12 \text{ s} \leq t \end{cases} \\ x(t=0) &= 1, \dot{x}(0) = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Figure 9: Harmonic Oscillator

Figure 10: Damped Harmonic Oscillator

Result of discontinuous harmonic oscillator as a graph is shown below:

Figure 11: Discontinuous Harmonic Oscillator

3.1.2 Keplerian 2-Body Problem

The plan in the sections that follow is to set up the computational framework and evaluate its accuracy in scenarios where the solution is either known or at least reasonably understood. Estimating very small numerical values is required to evaluate either numerical accuracy or the impacts of radiation pressure.

Because of the large difference between the masses, we can express it using M without including m in the equation as follows:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}} = -\frac{GM}{r^2} \hat{\mathbf{r}} \quad (10)$$

To find the gravitational coefficient needed to solve the equation, the following expression can be used $\mu \equiv GM$

$$\mu_{\oplus} \equiv GM_{\oplus} = 3.986004418 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}^2 \quad (11)$$

And Earth will be consider as a sphere with radius of $R_{\oplus}=6.371 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$

According to Feynman's lecture note equations of motion in this simple geometry expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{x} &= \dot{v}_x = -\mu_{\oplus} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{x}{r} = -\mu_{\oplus} \frac{x}{r^3} \\ \ddot{y} &= \dot{v}_y = -\mu_{\oplus} \frac{y}{r^3}\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

where $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$ Simplifying here, as in the harmonic oscillator, u can be defined this way.

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ v_x \\ v_y \end{pmatrix}$$

Notice that $x = u_1$ and $y = u_2$.

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{v}_x \\ \dot{v}_y \end{pmatrix}$$

Without air drag equations become shown:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{u}} &= \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{v}_x \\ \dot{v}_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -\mu_{\oplus}/r^3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\mu_{\oplus}/r^3 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ v_x \\ v_y \end{pmatrix} = A\mathbf{u}. \\ A &\equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -\mu_{\oplus}/r^3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\mu_{\oplus}/r^3 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.\end{aligned}\tag{13}$$

After numerical solution calculations for circular orbit of a satellite which have a radius of $a = 7095.5\text{km}$ without radiation pressure or drag we obtain orbit graph as

Figure 12: Lightsail Trajectory

We must simulate the radiation pressure affecting the sail in order to go forward. The sail is a perfect reflector of area A is the most straightforward approximation, one that must unquestionably be taken into serious consideration. In that situation, the overall solar pressure force is equal to:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{rad}} = \frac{2W_E}{c} A \cos^2 \theta \hat{\mathbf{n}}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{rad}} = \frac{2W_E}{c} A \hat{\mathbf{j}}$$

The Sun enters the shadow of the Earth if the coordinates of the spacecraft are $(+R_{\oplus}, y)$, with $y > 0$. Conversely, the Sun exits the shadow of the Earth if the coordinates of the spacecraft are $(-R_{\oplus}, y)$, with $y > 0$. Therefore the radiation force acting on the spacecraft in this model is:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{rad}} = \begin{cases} +\frac{2W_E}{c} A \hat{\mathbf{j}}, & \text{if } |x| \geq +R_{\oplus} \text{ and } y \geq 0 \\ +\frac{2W_E}{c} A \hat{\mathbf{j}}, & \text{if } y < 0 \\ 0 \hat{\mathbf{j}}, & \text{if } |x| < +R_{\oplus} \text{ and } y \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Here, the basic values needed to be input again, taking into consideration that the Earth's radius is crucial for accounting for solar eclipses and calculating the effects of radiation pressure. The values provided in Lightsail 2 reports. The radiation pressure by sail area at the Earth's surface was estimated to give a sense of the relative magnitude of the gravitational force and radiation force.

After that the radiation pressure causes an acceleration nearly 10^{-5} times that caused by the gravitational force of the Earth

Figure 13: Lightsail Trajectory With Radiation Pressure

Plotting the difference between the perturbed and the referred trajectory as a function of time allows us to track this solution once more. We will pay special attention to the semimajor axis that results from the osculating elements. The spacecraft's total specific energy at any given moment is:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}v^2 - \frac{G\mu_{\oplus}}{r}$$

Hence the instantaneous semimajor axis is

$$a = -\frac{\mu_{\oplus}}{2E}$$

Figure 14: Semimajor axis

We can now think about how regulating sail orientation will affect how the orbital elements change. The sail is instructed to change its orientation from parallel to the direction of light coming from the Sun (Sail "OFF") to perpendicular to that direction (Sail "ON") in order to enhance the energy of the spacecraft. In order to create these simulations, it is necessary to first define a function that is equal to 1 if the true anomaly θ of the spaceship, as determined from the x-axis, is $\theta \in [270, 90]$, i.e., the right two sectors of the plane, and 0 otherwise.

Figure 15: Semimajor axis with Solar Sailing

Now plotting with the previous calculation.

Figure 16: Sailing and Radiation Pressure

3.2 6-DOF Dynamic Model and Digital-Twin of CubeSat Targeting Mars

The main purpose of this study is to create a **Digital-Twin** of a CubeSat with **FOSS** applications. Therefore, after this part, **Xcos**, which is a block-based numerical calculation software, which is an add-on of **Scilab**, has been used for this purpose. This block-based dynamic model, which is relatively easy to read and build, and **Scilab**'s ability to read data from an external source can be used to create a **Digital-Twin** of CubeSat, which is our goal. By calculating and comparing the future situations with the instantaneous data coming from the sensors of a real CubeSat, one can increase the predictability of the system, know the instant and the past state of the system. At the same time, the "C" language code of the block diagram created can be written to a file by **Xcos**. And it can be said that the most important advantage of **Scilab/Xcos** over other similar programs that can do this is that it is an open-source and free program.

When constructing a dynamic model of a system, a careful and realistic mathematical description of each physical phenomenon and system is required. However, before these definitions and equations are written mathematically, an important point to be considered is that the axis system(s)

to be used should be determined in advance and the equations and assumptions should be made according to the system(s). Therefore, it would be correct to specify the axes sets used first. **NED** was used to create this system as body axes. The "N" (North) direction is towards the nose of the vehicle, the "E" (East) direction is towards the right side of the vehicle's nose, and the "Z" direction is towards the underside of the vehicle in accordance with the right hand rule. This set of axes is also shown visually below.

Figure 17: Traditional **NED** axis system

In the orbital calculations of CubeSat and planets, the Sun was chosen as the center of the inertial axis system, as it facilitates the calculations and is located at the center of the solar system.

After determining the axes to be worked on, the system can be started to be designed with blocks on **Xcos**. First of all, 9 planets in the solar system and the sun are included in the simulation of this mission. In this context, various superblocks have been written to find the gravitational forces between the planets, their positions, the forces on the CubeSat, and the thrust from the solar sail. The image below shows all the superblocks of CubeSat's **6-DOF** model.

The **6-DOF** model consists of six main blocks in total. These blocks compute these variables respectively as below;

- . Position of planets
- . Gravitational forces on the CubeSat
- . Thrust from the sail
- . Moments due to the thrust from the sail
- . **DCM**
- . Equations of motion (Position of the spacecraft)

Instead of getting the simulation results of this **6-DOF** CubeSat model immediately, testing the accuracy of all blocks one by one plays an important role in proving that the work done is healthy

Figure 18: 6-DOF CubeSat model diagram in Xcos

and in the reliability of the results obtained. Therefore, before showing the results, it was desired to verify the accuracy of each block independently or, if necessary, about each other. Of course, the accuracy of this model is doomed to be improved. Because of the limited time and manpower of the study, some simplifying assumptions must be made and since these assumptions caused the model of the system to move away from reality, it decreased its accuracy. Therefore, the following subsections will show the validation of each block separately.

3.2.1 Position of the Planets Block

Figure 19: Position of the Planets Block

This block is simply the block that finds the forces between the 9 planets in the solar system

using Newton’s gravitational law and then calculates their positions numerically during the integration time starting with some initial position and velocity values. The block contains two different types for each planet (except Pluto) and one for the gravitational effect of the sun, a total of 17 sub-blocks. Since the blocks made are repetitive of each other and there are many blocks, only the blocks that will find the position of the Earth will be examined as an example. Below are the inputs and outputs of the first of 3 separate blocks that will be used to calculate the Earth’s position.

Figure 20: Gravitational Force Magnitude Between Earth and Planets

This block takes the instantaneous positions of all planets according to the heliocentric inertial reference frame (now it will be expressed only as “with respect to sun”) as input and gives the gravitational force between the Earth and every planet non-directionally (only its magnitude).

Figure 21: Gravitational Force Magnitude Between Earth and Mars

The image above shows the block representations of some equations inside this block. Since the same process is repeated between Earth and other planets, only the equations between Earth and Mars have been shown here for simplicity. Simply, Newton's gravitational law and other formulas used in this calculation are given below.

$$F_G = \frac{GM_{Mars}M_{Earth}}{r_{dif}^2} \quad (15)$$

$$r_{dif} = r_{Earth} - r_{Mars} \quad (16)$$

$$r_{dif} = \sqrt{x_{dif}^2 + y_{dif}^2 + z_{dif}^2} \quad (17)$$

By repeating these processes for the other planets, only the magnitudes of the gravitational forces between the Earth and the other planets were obtained. Then, in the block seen below, the gravitational force between the Sun and the other planets was again found by Newton's law of gravitation.

Figure 22: Gravitational Force Magnitude Between Sun and Other Planets

Figure 23: Gravitational Force Magnitude Between Sun and Earth

Again, just for simplicity, just the force between Earth and Sun is shown above. Finally, the block that calculates the position of the Earth with respect to the Sun, using the force magnitudes between the Earth and other planets and the positions of the other planets relative to the Sun, is shown below.

Figure 24: Position of the Earth from the Sun

Figure 25: Position of the Earth from the Sun

In this block, where the position of the Earth around the Sun is calculated instantaneously, as can be seen in the example above, the difference between the position vectors of the Earth and each planet is taken first, and then this difference vector is divided by its size and a unit vector is obtained. Afterward, this obtained unit vector and the size of the gravitational force taken as input are multiplied by the dimensions on each axis, and a net and directional gravitational force is obtained. The formulations for this calculation can be seen below.

$$r_{dif} = r_{Sun} - r_{Earth} \quad (18)$$

$$\hat{r}_{dif} = \frac{|r_{dif}|}{r_{dif}} \quad (19)$$

$$F_{Grav} = |F_{Grav}| \cdot \hat{r}_{dif} \quad (20)$$

Figure 26: Position of the Earth from the Sun

In the last stage, net directional force vectors for each planet obtained were collected and turned into a single net directional force, then divided by the mass of the Earth, and net acceleration was obtained. Then, as a result of integrating this net acceleration vector twice numerically with respect to time, the position vector of the Earth with respect to the Sun was found. Equations related to that diagram are shown below.

$$F_{Net} = \sum F_{Grav} \quad (21)$$

$$a_{Net} = \frac{F_{Net}}{M_{Earth}} \quad (22)$$

$$P_{Earth} = \int \int a_{Net} \quad (23)$$

The verification of this block will be done in the next subsection, the block that computes the net gravitational force on CubeSat, since the methods and formulas used are the same.

3.2.2 Gravitational Forces on the CubeSat Block

Figure 27: Gravitational Forces on the CubeSat due to the Other Planets and Sun

In this block, since the same Newton's gravitational calculations in the planet position calculation blocks used in the previous section are made between CubeSat and other planets and the Sun, formulations are not shown again. Instead, this block will also be put into a test to test whether a correct result is obtained in this block and the previous section blocks.

For the test, it is sufficient to check the process in which the gravitational force between the CubeSat and the Sun is calculated. Calculated by hand, the force exerted on a 40 kg CubeSat at a distance of 300,000 km from the Sun is as follows.

$$F = \frac{6.6743 * (10^{-11}) * 1.989 * (10^{30}) * 40}{(3 * (10^8))^2} = 59,000.812N$$

As can be seen in the image above, the gravitational force resulting from a given distance only on the N axis turned out to be in the -N direction and the same size as the hand calculation.

3.2.3 Thrust from the Sail Block

Figure 28: Thrust from the sail

In this block, the thrust applied by the solar sail to the CubeSat is modeled. The formula used in

the propulsion model [[2]] shown below.

$$F_{Sail} = 9.113 \times 10^{-6} \left(\frac{RA}{D^2} \right) \sin^2 \theta \quad (24)$$

where R is the rate of incident photons, or in other words the efficiency of the sail, D is the sail's distance from the Sun (in AU), A is the sail's area in m^2 , and θ is the sail's orientation with respect to the Sun. For simplicity, an ideal sail is assumed (R is given) and the sail orientation angle is assumed to be a constant 90 degrees. The diagram below shows the Xcos diagram representation of the equation.

Figure 29: Thrust from the sail

In the following, it can be seen that the thrust on an ideal sail at 1 AU is calculated for the verification of this block. According to the [[5]], the thrust that occurs on an ideal sail, which is 1 AU away and has an area of 1 million m^2 , is said to be approximately 9 N, as calculated in the thrust block.

3.2.4 Moments Due to the Thrust From the Sail

Since the force applied to the CubeSat from the solar sail is not applied directly from the center of gravity, this force creates a torque on the hull of the CubeSat. After the calculation of these moments, the body angular velocity vectors are obtained according to the inertial axis system. The superblock which represents these calculations can be seen below.

Figure 30: Net Moments and Angular Velocities

While calculating the moment of inertia matrix, it is assumed that the CubeSat is symmetrical in the NE and ND planes for the sake of simplicity. Later, the lengths of the CubeSat were taken as 5X5X5 m from the center of mass. Also, for the sake of simplicity, the net thrust vector has always been affected without any distance from the center of mass in the E and D axes.

Figure 31: Net Moments and Angular Velocities

Above is the **Xcos** diagram of the equations expressed by the moment block. First of all, the thrust and moment arm vectors taken as input are multiplied in a way that does not create a roll moment in accordance with the assumption made above, and the torque vector is obtained. Later, the angular acceleration equation in the [4], which was examined in the literature review section, was directly applied. This formula is shown again below.

$$\dot{\omega}_B = -J^{-1}(\omega_B \times (J\omega_B)) + J^{-1}T_B \quad (25)$$

Finally, the body angular velocities (p,q,r) are obtained by integrating the body angular acceleration vector obtained from the above formula with respect to time and the inertial axis. In order to verify the block, the block was removed from the system and a thrust force was applied independently, and it was tested whether it had any angular velocity (that is, whether there was any moment) as a result of integration.

As expected, a thrust vector directed through the positive E direction and has a positive N-direction distance from the center of mass gave the CubeSat a positive angular velocity in a D-direction in accordance with the right-hand rule.

We see above that a force applied in the N direction and at a distance N does not create a moment due to any angular velocity as expected.

However, in the above case, contrary to expectations, no roll rate occurs. In fact, the reason for this is related to the assumptions we have made at the beginning. Since the equations are constructed with the assumption that the thrust is always not far from the center of mass in the E and D directions, neither combination should be expected to produce a roll rate or roll moment.

3.2.5 DCM Blok

The superblock that forms the **DCM**, which provides the conversion from the Body axis to the Inertial axis or from the Inertial Axis to the Body axis, is as seen above. The **Xcos** diagram is also shown below.

In the method used in the diagram, firstly, **DCM** which converts the body angular velocities to the orientation rates of the body with respect to the inertial axis, multiplied by the body angular velocities, and then the body orientation angles rates are found. After that step by integrating these rates with respect to time, body orientation angles (ϕ, θ, ψ) are found. Then these outputs made an input to the **DCM**'s to complete the loop. **DCM** structures are shown in the below diagrams:

Figure 32: **DCM** from Euler angle rates to body angular velocities

Figure 33: **DCM** from body to inertial axis system

As usual, this block was isolated and tested for certain values of ϕ , θ and ψ for validation purposes,

and the results were checked with results from similar software, Matlab/Simulink **DCM** blocks with the same Euler angles as inputs.

Figure 34: **DCM** created with **Xcos**

Figure 35: **DCM** created with Simulink

As can be clearly seen, **DCM** blocks created with **Xcos** and **DCM** obtained from Simulink block exactly match for the same Euler angles.

3.2.6 Equations of Motion (Position of the CubeSat)

Figure 36: Equations of Motion (Position of the CubeSat)

Finally, all applied forces (thrust and gravitational force), body rotation rates and **DCMs** on the CubeSat were given as input to the EOM block, and the instantaneous position of the CubeSat relative to the Sun was calculated.

Figure 37: Equations of Motion (Position of the CubeSat)

To summarize the above processes briefly, firstly, the thrust force obtained from the body axis was expressed in the inertial axis using **DCM**, then the net gravitational force and this converted thrust force were added together to find the final force. Then, this net force is divided by the CubeSat's mass and its instantaneous acceleration is then integrated twice consecutively to obtain the instantaneous position vector relative to the Sun.

Instead of directly verifying this block, it was desired to verify the thrust subtracted version for simplicity. The purpose of this test is to observe the rotation of an object with initial velocity and position, on which only gravitational force is applied, around a large mass object. Thanks to this test, both gravity and EOM blocks can be verified. The schematics of the block are shown below, respectively.

Figure 38: Equations of Motion (Position of the CubeSat without thrust)

Figure 39: Gravitational force block for test

Figure 40: Orbit of a CubeSat around another heavy planet

3.3 Pinto F. Orbit Simulation with Xcos

It can be simulated the motion of a spacecraft propelled by solar sails around a planet. The spacecraft will start its movement from certain velocity and place. With using Newton's law of motion this elliptical movement can be calculated. According to this situation planet will have force on spacecraft which is equal to a constant times the product of the planet's mass and the spacecraft's mass divided by the square of the distance.

The motion of solar sail propelled CubeSat is calculated by this Xcos blocks and visualized.

Figure 41: Xcos Diagram of Orbit Calculations.

The middle part is calculating acceleration and velocity, bottom left is thrust equation for solar sails, bottom right calculate on-off maneuver with respect to the angle between the sun and solar sail, middle right is used for visualizing the motion.

To explain this figure used formulas given below;

$$\begin{aligned}
m_i \frac{dv_{ix}}{dt} &= \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{Gm_i m_j (x_i - x_j)}{r_{ij}^3} \\
m_i \frac{dv_{iy}}{dt} &= \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{Gm_i m_j (y_i - y_j)}{r_{ij}^3} \\
m_i \frac{dv_{iz}}{dt} &= \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{Gm_i m_j (z_i - z_j)}{r_{ij}^3}
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Further, it can be define r_{ij} as the distance between the two object i and j ; this is equal to

$$r_{ij} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2 + (z_i - z_j)^2}.$$

Figure 42: Result of Xcos Orbit Calculations.

Figure 43: Result of on and off maneuver.

4 Conclusion

To sum up, [Digital-Twin](#) technology has become a game-changer in the realm of space missions, providing unheard-of capabilities for exploring, monitoring, and improving planetary and spacecraft systems. We have examined the fundamental elements and uses of [Digital-Twins](#) in space missions throughout this work, emphasizing their contribution to better mission planning, spacecraft design, operational effectiveness, and data analysis. [Digital-Twins](#) give scientists and engineers the ability to simulate and predict a variety of mission scenarios, assisting in the optimization of mission parameters and lowering of risks. When real-time sensor data is combined with advanced analytics, situational awareness is improved, allowing for proactive decision-making and adaptive mission control.

We have talked about how [Digital-Twins](#) make it possible to model and simulate intricate space systems, making it easier to spot potential problems and take preventative measures. This ability is essential for long-duration operations, where the capacity to predict and address unforeseen difficulties is of the utmost importance. We have also looked into the use of [Digital-Twins](#) to facilitate the processing and interpretation of the enormous volumes of data gathered during space missions. [Digital-Twins](#) provide insights into the behavior of spacecraft and planetary systems by merging data from numerous sources and employing cutting-edge algorithms, boosting scientific discoveries and enabling more informed decision-making.

Despite the enormous potential of [Digital-Twin](#) technology in space missions, there are still issues to be solved. Among them are assuring the dependability and quality of virtual models, fusing information from various sources, and getting over the space-based communication and computational resource constraints. Future developments in [Digital-Twin](#) technology, together with those in AI, machine learning, and autonomous systems, will pave the way for new frontiers in space travel. Future space missions are expected to greatly benefit from the use of [Digital-Twins](#), opening the door to more ambitious projects like long-duration human spaceflight, planetary colonization, and

interstellar exploration.

In conclusion, [Digital-Twin](#) technology has transformed the world of space missions by delivering insightful data, streamlining processes, and improving decision-making. [Digital-Twins](#) will likely become essential instruments as we travel farther into space, assisting us in overcoming the difficulties of deep space research and unlocking the secrets of the cosmos.

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